

COMPREHENSIVE EXAMINATION OF WOMEN 3 YEARS AFTER AKI AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF PREECLAMPSIA

Radjabov R.K.

Bukhara State Medical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14630669>

Relevance. In numerous works devoted to acute renal failure (ARF), not all aspects have been sufficiently covered. This is especially true for ARF of obstetric etiology, which is given undeservedly little attention, because in most countries with a high birth rate, ARF caused by pathology of pregnancy and childbirth occurs in 50 - 70% of cases in the structure of all etiological factors leading to this complication. A few works by domestic authors clearly show the high frequency of development (50 - 70%) of ARF of obstetric etiology, the severity of its clinical course and the stability of high mortality rates within (30 - 40%). Numerous features of the development, course and outcomes of ARF caused by pathology of pregnancy in various regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan are shown, many unresolved issues, which directly or indirectly cause such disappointing results.

Purpose of the study. Study of the features of a comprehensive examination of women 3 years after acute renal failure against the background of preeclampsia and anemia.

Material and research methods. This group consisted of 16 women, whose age was between 24 and 29 years (26.1±2.7 years).

Four of the examined women continued to have pale skin and pastosity of the distal parts of the legs. In 12 (75%) of the examined women in this group, normalization of menstrual function was noted, whereas in the four women described above, obvious disorders were noted. Three of the women we examined had headaches and high blood pressure. Clinical and biochemical studies conducted upon admission confirmed the presence of anemia. Both the CF and CR remained underestimated, being within 0.82–0.96 ml/s and 93–95%. In all cases, ultrasound of the kidneys continued to note some increase in their size with increased echogenicity, thickening of the cortex (TPP=2.7±0.4 mm) and expansion of the renal pelvis.

Results. Summarizing all the data obtained from clinical, biochemical and instrumental studies of women who suffered acute renal failure after 3 years, the following can be noted: generalized vascular spasm caused by PE leads to deterioration of blood flow in almost all organs and systems, including the kidneys. All of this is accompanied by significant arterial hypertension, azotemia.

References:

1. Tatina ES Esilbaeva BT at.all “Aktuall research of population health state in the Aral Sea at modern conditions” No. 9, 2014.
2. Alimbetova V.S., Kosnazarov K.A. Pollution of atmospheric air in the Republic of Karakalpakstan and its impact on the health of the population. Journal of Theoretical and Clinical Medicine, 2006, No. 5, pp. 28-29
3. Republican scientific and practical conference “Factors influencing the health of the population in the Aral Sea region”, dedicated to the 15th anniversary of the Nukus branch of TashPMI November 21, 2006

4. Zhumatova M.G., Loshkin V.N. Problems of women's reproductive health. Problems of reproduction-2010 №3 p-24-27
5. Avakov V.E., et al. Acute renal failure of obstetric etiology. Current state of the problem // Journal of Theoretical and Clinical Medicine, 2000, No. 6, 6-8.
6. A.Yu. Borisov, T.V. Raskina Early diagnostics of acute kidney injury/ Actamedica Eurasica 2016. No. 1
7. Smirnov A.V., Dobronravov V.A., Rumyantsev A.Sh., Kayukov I.G. Acute kidney injury. MIA, No. 2. 2016; IOSR Journal of Dental and Medical Sciences March 2015.

